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INTERFERENCE FACTORS OF TEACHER DEVELOPMENT IN THE MAGELANG DISTRICT, INDONESIA

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This study aims to analyse the factors, inhibiting the promotion of teachers in the Magelang regency. The factors, predicted in this study, include age, rules, comfort, motivation, and education. The research approach used is quantitative methods. Respondents, who participated in this study, were 116 people. The analysis used is a multiple regression test. Demographic data shows that the respondents, involved in this study, were dominated by female respondents, namely 89 people (76 %) and male respondents totalling 27 people (23.28 %). Meanwhile, there were 84 respondents (72.41 %) under 45 years old and 32 respondents aged 45 years and over (27.59 %). As many as 83 respondents (71.55 %) during the last 4 years have never been promoted and as many as 33 respondents (28.45 %) have not been promoted for 5 years or even more than 5 years. In connection with this promotion, as many as 96 respondents (82.76 %) said that they wanted to be promoted, but as many as 20 respondents (17.24 %) had no desire to be promoted. Meanwhile, as many as 79 respondents (68.10 %) felt it was difficult to get promoted and the remaining 37 respondents (31.90 %) did not feel difficulties. The results showed that the age factor has a probability of 0,000 and the comfort factor has a probability of 0.036 and has a significant effect on the difficulty in advancing according to the respondents in this study. Meanwhile, the factors of regulation, motivation, and education do not significantly influence the difficulty of promotion for teachers

Keywords: inhibitors, promotion, promotion, rank, teacher

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1. Introduction

This study aims to analyse the factors, inhibiting the promotion of teachers in the Magelang regency, Indonesia. This research is important to do as an effort to find a strategic way to spur teacher promotion after knowing the factors that can hinder teacher promotion.

Teacher is a profession, which of course requires professionalism for those, who live it, and of course also requires commitment. As a profession, a teacher deserves to be promoted or get promoted through the applicable procedures. The procedures, governing promotion in Indonesia, are contained in State Gazette No. 865/3 dated April 3, 1995 which also regulates the recruitment and salary of teachers [1] and is formulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 35 of 2010 and Regulation of the Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 13 of 2019 concerning Proposing, Determining, and Fostering Functional Positions for Civil Servants. The latest policy states that teachers can be promoted every 2 years.

2. Literature review

Promotion for teachers is closely related to the determination of a credit score which will encourage teachers to always improve their professionalism as well as the most important reward or gift for a teacher, including those, who are currently serving as school principals [2]. In addition, it is necessary to convey that promotion can have a good impact on teacher work performance [3].

Promotion for teachers is related to teacher careers, and the factors that contribute to the success of teacher careers are experience, education, seniority, interpersonal skills, superior abilities, commitment and dedication, support from superiors, colleagues and family, and leadership style. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factors are family preference, limited access to professional training, personality, lack of leadership charisma, lack of confidence, community expectations, gender bias, lack of qualifications, power, informal networks, no mentoring system, low self-esteem, and if the profession is not taken seriously [4, 5].

Promotion opportunities encourage teachers to improve their abilities [6] and effective teachers have the opportunity to be promoted and have the opportunity to earn greater annual income [7, 8]. Meanwhile, to facilitate the teacher promotion process requires promotional training [9] and university involvement [10, 11].

The function of teacher promotion is to improve teacher performance including increasing teacher attendance because improving teacher performance is not enough just to use supervision without intensive giving or promotion [12]. In addition, promotions can also be used as an appreciation for the quality of teaching that has been carried out by teachers [13, 14].

Teacher is a good profession, and not everyone can be a good teacher, even in some countries it has been proven to have suffered from a shortage of teachers [15–17]. Therefore, teachers are required to always improve their professionalism using various methods, one of which is through continuous teacher professional

development. Continuous teacher professional development means teachers need to continuously update their knowledge and skills throughout their career [18–20].

Career-related socialization in the teaching profession involves a complex negotiation process in a dynamic network of relationships that occur within and around schools [21]. Meanwhile, to find out how high the increase in teacher professionalism is, one can use the exam model [22].

Regarding the promotion of teachers, those with high work involvement and teachers, who are responsible for service and management, have a tendency to attend various trainings to improve their careers [23]. They certainly understand the various challenges and opportunities in the career advancement process that are framed in the teacher promotion program. The many challenges that are present in the teacher promotion process also present many opportunities in it [24].

Promotion practices for teachers can actually be done automatically, but it requires systematic implementation guidelines, without systematic implementation guidelines it will cause many negative effects, such as low workforce and low attendance [25] as a result they will think that without hard work they will still be promoted regularly.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

This study aims to analyse the factors, inhibiting the promotion of teachers, in the Magelang regency. The factors, predicted in this study, include age, rules, comfort, motivation, and education. To achieve this goal, the researchers have carried out several activities, namely as follows.

a. Before conducting the research, the researcher made observations at the research location to see the conditions that occurred related to the difficulties, experienced by the teacher in making promotions.

b. Researchers collect and study many articles as references to strengthen researchers' understanding of the topics under study, namely the factors that hinder the increase in teachers.

4. Method

This research is a quantitative study, using a questionnaire as an instrument. The item, used in the questionnaire, uses a Likert scale, namely number 1 represents strongly disagree, number 2 represents disagree, number 3 represents neutral, number 4 represents agree, and number 5 represents strongly agree [26]. The questionnaire, used in the form of a survey, consists of questions on the demographics of the respondents and questions, used to determine the attributes that hinder the promotion of teachers in the Magelang regency, Central Java.

The attributes that are predicted to be an indicator of the difficulty of teachers in making promotions are age, rules, comfort, motivation, and education (fig 1). The selection of these attributes is of course based on the results of previous observations, made by the researchers and based on various theories that have been studied previously.

Fig. 1. Hypothesis Diagram

Based on this diagram, the hypotheses, proposed in this study, are as follows.

H1. There is a positive effect of age on the difficulty of promotion of a teacher

H2. There is a positive effect of the rules on the difficulty of promotion of a teacher

H3. There is a positive effect of comfort on the difficulty of promotion of a teacher

H4. There is a positive effect of motivation on the difficulty of promotion of a teacher

H5. There is a positive effect of education on the difficulty of promotion of teachers

Based on the hypothesis, proposed in this study, the statistical analysis method is used to determine the factors that affect the difficulty of teacher promotion together with statistical methods of multiple regression analysis. This analysis is also used to rank the factors from the most to the least influence on the difficulty of increasing teachers.

5. Result

5.1. Demographics of respondents

The demographic data of respondents obtained provide a lot of important information that can be conveyed. Based on the results of the study, it shows that the respondents, involved in this study, were dominated by female respondents, namely 89 people (76 %) and male respondents totalling 27 people (23.28 %). Meanwhile, there were 84 respondents (72.41 %) under 45 years old and 32 respondents aged 45 years and over (27.59 %) (Table 1).

Of all respondents, involved in this study, as many as 111 people (95.69 %) were currently serving as teachers and as many as 5 people (4.31 %) were currently serving as school principals. Meanwhile, respondents, who had rank II, were 4 people (3.45 %), those, who had rank III, were 100 people (86.21 %), and those, who had rank IV, were 12 people (10.34 %). (Table 1).

As many as 83 respondents (71.55 %) during the last 4 years have never been promoted and as many as 33 respondents (28.45 %) have not been promoted for 5 years or even more than 5 years. In connection with this promotion, as many as 96 respondents (82.76 %) said that they wanted to be promoted, but as many as 20 respondents (17.24 %) had no desire to be promoted. Meanwhile, as many as 79 respond-

ents (68.10 %) felt it was difficult to get promoted and the remaining 37 respondents (31.90 %) did not feel difficulties (Table 1).

Table 1

Demographics of respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1. Gender		
Women	89	76.72
Male	27	23.28
2. Age		
< 45 years	84	72.41
≥ 45 years	32	27.59
3. Position		
Classroom teacher	111	95.69
Principal	5	4.31
4. Rank		
II	4	3.45
III	100	86.21
IV	12	10.34
5. A period of stagnation (not yet promoted)		
< 4 years	83	71.55
≥ 5 years	33	28.45
6. Desire for promotion		
YES	96	82.76
NO	20	17.24
7. Finding it difficult to move up the ranks		
YES	79	68.10
NO	37	31.90

5.2. Results of multiple regression analysis

The multiple regression analysis, used in this study, aims to determine whether the factors, used as the independent variables, are able to predict the difficulty of teachers in promotion. Based on the results of the study, it shows the ability of the factors, which are used as independent variables, to predict the difficulty

of teachers in promotion by 19.7 %, which is indicated by a R square value of 0.197. Meanwhile, the resulting F value is 5.397 with a significance value of 0.000. These results indicate that the model, used in this study, is a significant model, namely that the factors of age, rules, comfort, motivation, and education are simultaneously able to predict the difficulty of teachers in promotion (Table 2).

Partially, the results of the analysis that have been carried out show that the age variable has a value of $\beta = 0.358$ with a significance value of 0.000 ($P < 0.05$), which indicates that the age variable has a significant positive effect on the difficulty of teachers in promotion. Meanwhile, the rule variable has a value of $\beta = 0.024$ with a significance value of 0.816 ($P > 0.05$), these results indicate that the rule variable has no significant effect on the difficulty of teachers in promotion (Table 2).

Another independent variable, namely the comfort variable, has a value of $\beta = -0.231$ with a significance value of 0.036 ($P < 0.05$), which indicates that the comfort variable has a negative and significant effect on the difficulty of teachers in promotion. Next is the motivation variable, the motivation variable has a value of $\beta = 0.010$ with a significance value of 0.921 ($P > 0.05$), which indicates that the motivation variable does not have a significant effect on the difficulty of teachers in promotion. Finally, the education variable has a value of $\beta = 0.093$ with a significance value of 0.361 ($P > 0.05$), which indicates that the education variable does not have a significant effect on the difficulty of teachers in promotion (Table 2).

Based on all the results of the analysis, age and comfort variables partially affect the difficulty of teachers in promotion, but the comfort variable has a negative effect on the difficulty of teachers in advancing the ranks. Meanwhile, the rules variable, motivation variable, and education variable did not have a significant effect on the difficulty of teachers in promotion.

Table 2

Results of multiple regression analysis

Model	Standardized coefficients		Adjusted R Square	F	Sig
	Beta	Sig			
(Constant)			0.197	5.397	0.000
Age	0.358	0.000			
Rules	0.024	0.816			
Comfort	-0.231	0.036			
Motivation	0.010	0.921			
Education	0.093	0.361			

6. Discussion

Based on the research results that have been shown, we can see that as many as 83 respondents (71.55 %) have never been promoted during the last 4 years and as many as 33 respondents (28.45 %) have never been promoted during 5 years and even more. These results indicate that in general the respondents have a high willingness to be promoted, but on the other hand there are 28.45 %, who have not been promoted for 5 years or more, this indicates that there are some proce-

dures that cannot be passed by the teachers, so they are unable to move up the ranks.

The desire of the teachers to be promoted is very high, based on the results of the research, reaching 82.76 %, while those, who do not wish to be promoted, are only 17.24 %. Even though the percentage of those, who wanted to be promoted, is relatively high, 68.10 % felt that it was difficult for them to be promoted and those, who did not find it difficult to get promoted, were

only 31.90 %. This difficulty is normal because there are many obstacles in getting promoted [24] and to make it easier, training is done first [9].

Based on the results of the analysis that has been carried out, we can see that the age variable has a value of $\beta = 0.358$ with a significance value of 0.000 ($P < 0.05$), which indicates that the age variable has a significant positive effect on the difficulty of teachers in promotion. These results indicate that the older the teacher becomes, the more difficult he/she will be in promotion.

This can be seen as reasonableness because the older a person is, the more complex the problems he/she will face, therefore if the teacher's age increases and he/she does not get assistance in advancing the ranks, he/she will have more difficulty, especially in the process of promotion, so need assistance. Apart from mentoring, another aspect that can disrupt a teacher from getting promoted when he/she gets older is the aspect of self-confidence. If the self-confidence in a teacher fades with age, then he/she will have a tendency to have difficulties in getting promoted because doing a promotion really requires aspects of self-confidence [5].

Another possible aspect that can hinder teachers from advancing in rank is the fact that promotion is a direction that is in line with the increase in teacher professionalism, so that if you want to be promoted, you must be willing to increase professionalism, while teachers, who are getting older, will of course have lower morale if must continue to spur his/her professionalism, especially economically enough in his/her life.

The factor that further hinders teacher promotion is the comfort factor. Based on the research results that have been described, the comfort factor has a value of $\beta = -0.231$ with a significance value of 0.036 ($p < 0.05$), which indicates that the comfort variable has a negative and significant effect on the difficulty of teachers in promotion. These all show that the more comfortable the condition of a teacher, the more it will prevent them from getting promoted. Conversely, the more uncomfortable they are, the easier it will be for them to get promoted, which can be caused by a desire

that when they get promoted, they expect to be more prosperous.

Limitations of the study. This research has been carried out well, but there are several weaknesses in this study, namely, a) the number of schools that are the research sites is still limited, b) the number of meticulous attributes is still limited. Therefore, it is hoped that future researchers can conduct research using more attributes and have wider research area coverage.

7. Conclusion

The results of observations that have been carried out by the researchers show that as many as 83 respondents (71.55 %) during the last 4 years have never been promoted and as many as 33 respondents (28.45 %) have never been promoted during 5 years or even more. In connection with this promotion, as many as 96 respondents (82.76 %) said that they wanted to be promoted, but as many as 20 respondents (17.24 %) had no desire to be promoted. Meanwhile, as many as 79 respondents (68.10 %) felt it was difficult to get promoted and the remaining 37 respondents (31.90 %) did not feel difficulties.

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been done, it can be concluded, that age can inhibit the promotion of teachers with a probability value of 0,000 and the comfort factor has a negative effect on the difficulty of teachers in advancing with a probability value of 0.036. Meanwhile, rules, motivation, and education do not have a significant effect on the difficulty of teachers in making promotions.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusions in this study, the recommendation that needs to be considered is that the government should always provide assistance to teachers in making promotions, especially for teachers, who are over 45 years of age. In addition, the government must always socialize that promotion is not only for teachers, who are already prosperous / comfortable, but for all teachers in order to improve teacher professionalism.

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